

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: AHMED****FIRST NAME: ABDULRAHMAN ADAMU****PROGRAM CODE: PHGH****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (in-text/parenthetical)

The author did did *not* use Zotero to insert references

The author did did *not* use Grammarly Premium (EUCLID provides access)

The author used the following software: (MSWord 2016 on Windows 10)

List your 7 key concepts with page number in text (then bold these terms in your RP)(samples below):

1. Essay Writing (EUCLID 2019, 1-4)
2. Plagiarism (EUCLID 2019, 5-6)
3. Literature review (EUCLID 2019, 17-22)
4. American Vs British English (EUCLID 2019, 27-35)
5. Chicago Style and Usage (EUCLID 2019, 44-47)

THE FIRST STEP TOWARDS KNOWLEDGE IS TO KNOW THAT WE ARE IGNORANT

1)INTRODUCTION

I have been writing in English for some time without formally learning how to write, and most of my writing skills came from passive knowledge through reading of other people writing and coping their style. I have never for once use my time to learn how to write in English rather I learn what I need to write when the need arises. Going through the course pack for ACA-401D period one, I realize that I am ignorant of English writing because what I know about English writing is just a tip of the iceberg. The ACA-401D period one course pack and the introductory video gave me an insight on the expectations on me during my study, while the Basic ACA-401D Tutorial video guide me on how to write my response paper, from how to personalize the response paper template, to the rule of style, paragraph style and citation. For the first time, I came to know about Zotero and how to link its extension with the chrome browser, however, I am still having difficulty-integrating it with my Microsoft Word 2016 on Window 10, which I believe it will become clearer in due course as I proceed with my learning.

2) KNOWING THE BASICS OF ESSAY WRITING

I never know the importance of follow the steps of essay writing, but it became clear to me that it is a linear process working through the different stages several times while writing my essay (EUCLID 2019, 1). Knowing that there is need to write the first draft to try out the structure and framework of my essay and how it will help me answer the question and the evidence and examples to use in structuring my arguments are new concept to me. I came to understand that the structure would give my essay an outlook and make it flow in a systematic way. One important aspect about easy writing is the paragraph, which need to deal with one main point with a topic sentence, supporting sentences, evidence and analysis of the evidence then Finishing with a critical conclusion (EUCLID 2019, 3).

The protector of an academic writing is referencing because it protects the integrity of the writer and acknowledge the owner of the write up because referencing guards against plagiarism. Finally, my essays will be improving by careful editing, sometimes it entails putting my essay aside for a few days before beginning to edit. This gives me time to think further about my answer and arguments and return to my work with a fresh perspective, notwithstanding keeping the deadline of submission in mind (EUCLID 2019, 4).

3) PLAGIARISM

Before reading this course material, I never know the full definition of Plagiarism, my earlier thought was that coping another person assignment is plagiarism s later come to know that plagiarism is using a source of information without giving credit to the author of that source of information. Now I know that the definition of plagiarism is wider than my thought, it is taking someone else's words or ideas, such as quoting, paraphrasing, copying, and pasting from the internet and not giving credit to the author. On the other hand, having someone write a paper for you and then putting your name on it and giving it to your professor would be plagiarism. The best way to avoid plagiarism is through proper citation, which could be in-text citation and list of works cited (EUCLID 2019, 5-6).

In-text citation used mainly for quotation and paraphrase refers to citing a piece of work used within the actual text itself. For example, "Before 1984, footnotes and endnotes were used in research reports. In certain instances, this form of documentation is still correct" (Gerson and Gerson 143). Quotation are the exact words of an author, short quotation is written within a quotation mark while long quotation are written as a separate paragraph using a quote style. On the other hand, paraphrase are the ideas and information that an author has produced on a topic but written in your own words and style and ensuring that the meaning remains with a logical flow (EUCLID 2019, 7-13).

4) LITERATURE REVIEW

Literature reviews start with introducing me to eleven key concept that need consideration while reviewing literature. Very interestingly are the proper uses of "its" and "it's," I came to know that it is impossible for a man to eat its cake and have it, also note that you are responsible for your decision. In the use of comma before the "and" in a list of items, the writer with examples, explain ant quote that “The INCLUSION of the final comma will never increase ambiguity in a sentence, while the EXCLUSION of the comma sometimes will. Likewise, the EXCLUSION of the comma will never increase the effectiveness of a sentence, while INCLUSION often will”. In essence, you need to include the final comma to be in the safer side (EUCLID 2019, 20). The writer was kind enough to direct me to go through several books, journals, articles, and dictionary but came up with no contrary statement.

5) American vs. British English

American English is currently the dominant form of English globally, this is due to several factors which includes: population, wealth, magnitude of higher education publishing industries, global mass media and media technology influence in America vs. the U.K. appeal of American popular culture on language and habits and the international political and economic position of the U.S. (EUCLID 2019, 27).

American and British English are both variants of World English. As such, they are more similar than different. The general categories of difference between standard American English (SAE) and standard British English (SBE) each have their own sociolectic value: Such as Different Pronunciation, Although Same Spelling, Different Spelling, Although Same Pronunciation, Same Term, Different but Similar Spelling and Pronunciation, Same Words, But Different or Additional Meanings (EUCLID 2019, 29).

However, I came to know that the difference and similarities of both British and American English did not happen by chance but has both historical and rhetorical origin and meaning which help me to understand the difference better, this also include the understanding of the influence of Euphemistic References, Equality, Politically Correctness, Ethnolects, Yiddish and Ethnic Jewish, Various Jargons.

6) CHICAGO STYLE AND USAGE

The Chicago style and usage start with introduction on the type of dictionary and recommended the use of Webster’s Third New *International Dictionary* and its chief abridgment, *Merriam-Webster’s Collegiate Dictionary*. It added that when more than one spelling is given, or more than one form of the pleural, Chicago always opts for the first form listed, thus aiding consistency. It then proceeds to explain the general rules of abbreviation, which are used in the beginning of a sentence, traditional form and scholarly abbreviation. It ended with the quotation (EUCLID 2019, 44).

“Abbreviations should be used only in contexts where they are clear to readers. . . . Writers and editors should monitor the number of different abbreviations used in a document; readers are trying to keep track of a large number of abbreviations, especially unfamiliar ones, will lose their way” (CMS 2003, 558).

Acronyms when first used in the text, an acronym must be introduced. This is done by placing the acronym or its source phrase in parentheses, and thereafter using just the acronym. Plural form of an acronym is written without an apostrophe; for example, write, the Master of Business Administration (MBA) program is popular at the university because MBAs command high starting salaries (EUCLID 2019, 44).

Capitalization may follow three forms: full caps, heading caps, or sentence caps. Full caps capitalize every character of every word. These are used only in major headings. Heading caps capitalize the first character of each word, subject to exceptions listed: the first and last words and all nouns, pronouns, adjectives, and subordinating conjunctions. Also, capitalize the first character after a colon in a title or heading. Otherwise, do not capitalize articles, prepositions, conjunctions, and infinitive. Sentence caps capitalize the first word of a title or heading, the first word after a colon, and proper nouns (EUCLID 2019, 45).

7) CONCLUSION

I have attended several online classis and program but reading ACA-401D period one (1) coursepack and orientation documents and to watch the videos presented by Prof. Laurent Cleenewerck made me to realize that the teaching methodology is different. However, the flexibility nature of the program will allow me to work at my own pace and grab the key concept needed for me to benefit maximally from this course.

This course had checkmated my basic knowledge of English and has answered several ambiguities I usually face when writing. It also made me understand why I usually failed to be selected when I write for any competitive application despite having the best argument and reasons to be selected. From now on, my work will be in consistent with the writing rules and regulations and with practice will perfect my skills in paraphrasing and used of Grammarly keeping in mind the format and style check of EUCLID’s checklist for papers and Turabian style.

REFERENCES

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma, 2nd ed. 2019. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. Bangui, Central African Republic: Euclid University.

The University of Chicago Press. "The Chicago Manual of Style Online." <https://www.chicagomanualofstyle.org/qanda/data/faq/topics/SpecialCharacters/faq0002.html> (accessed Mach 27, 2021).

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. *ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1*. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.